

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
КЛИНИК ТИББИЁТ
АХБОРОТНОМАСИ**

**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

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**BULLETIN OF FUNDAMENTAL
AND CLINIC MEDICINE**

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА КЛИНИК
ТИББИЁТ АХБОРОТНОМАСИ
ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF THE BLOOD CONDITION OF WOMEN IN THE EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF POSTPARTUM SEPSIS

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Resume. Postpartum sepsis is a generalized inflammatory reaction caused by the penetration of pathogenic microorganisms into the blood after childbirth. It can develop both after natural childbirth and after cesarean section. In conditions of sepsis, deep activation of the hemostasis system occurs, often leading to the development of disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC syndrome). Changes in the hemostasis chart can precede the clinical picture, which makes it an important tool for early diagnosis.

Keywords: Postpartum sepsis, hemostasis, blood test, early diagnosis

ТУҒРУҚДАН КЕЙИНГИ СЕПСИСНИ ЭРТА ТАШХИСЛАШДА АЁЛЛАРНИНГ ҚОН ХОЛАТИНИ ҚИЁСИЙ БАҲОЛАШ

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Резюме. Туғруқдан кейинги сепсис туғруқдан кейин патоген микроорганизмларнинг қонга кириши натижасида юзага келадиган умумий яллиғланиш реакциясидир. У табиий туғруқдан кейин ҳам, кесарча кесишдан кейин ҳам ривожланиши мумкин. Сепсис шароитида гемостаз тизимининг чуқур фаоллашуви содир бўлади, бу кўпинча тарқоқ томир ичи қон ивиши (ДВС-синдром) ривожланишига олиб келади. Гемостазиограммадаги ўзгаришлар клиник кўринишдан олдин содир бўлиши мумкин, бу эса уни эрта таъхис қўйишининг муҳим воситасига айлантиради.

Калит сўзлар: Туғруқдан кейинги сепсис, гемостазиограмма, қон таҳлили, эрта таъхис

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНАЯ ОЦЕНКА СОСТОЯНИЯ КРОВИ ЖЕНЩИН ПРИ РАННЕЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ПОСЛЕРОДОВОГО СЕПСИСА

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Резюме. Послеродовой сепсис — это генерализованная воспалительная реакция, вызванная проникновением патогенных микроорганизмов в кровь после родов. Он может развиваться как после естественных родов, так и после кесарева сечения. В условиях сепсиса происходит глубокая активация системы гемостаза, часто приводящая к развитию диссеминированного внутрисосудистого свертывания (ДВС-синдрома). Изменения в гемостазиограмме могут предшествовать клинической картине, что делает её важным инструментом ранней диагностики.

Ключевые слова: Послеродовой сепсис, гемостазиограмма, анализ крови, ранняя диагностика

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Introduction. In 2013, more than 30,000 maternal deaths (11%) were caused by postpartum sepsis, which is the third most common cause of approximately 290,000 maternal deaths worldwide [1, 2]. Almost all of these cases occurred in low-income countries. The region with the highest proportion of maternal mortality due to sepsis was South Asia (14%) [3]. Postpartum sepsis can be easily prevented with affordable and relatively inexpensive measures. Historical data show a marked decrease in maternal mortality in developed countries in the middle of the 20th century.; A significant proportion of this decrease was due to the prevention and proper treatment of maternal infections and sepsis [4]. Before the advent of antibiotics and etiological studies, the mortality rate exceeded 20% [5, 6]. With proper antibiotic treatment [7], the mortality rate can decrease to 2% [8].

The incidence of sepsis is 20 times higher than the mortality rate, and complications include septicemia, shock, peritonitis, or the formation of abscesses requiring surgical intervention [9, 10]. Long-term consequences, especially with untimely or incomplete treatment, include chronic pelvic inflammatory diseases and bilateral tubal occlusion, which leads to decreased fertility in the future [4]. In addition, there is a serious risk of transmission of infection to newborns either vertically during the prenatal period or through direct contact during childbirth [9, 10].

The frequency of postpartum sepsis (PPS) varies from country to country and ranges from 2 to 10% and depends on risk factors, which include the place of birth (in a medical facility or at home), low socio-economic status, poor nutrition, anemia, prolonged labor, premature discharge of amniotic fluid, multiple pregnancies, primiparous a woman, overweight and type of delivery (cesarean section or vaginal delivery), more than 5 vaginal examinations during childbirth, other obstetric manipulations, lack of antibiotic prophylaxis, and other factors [1,3]. The World Health Organization (WHO) used a 5% incidence estimate for the Global Burden of Disease (GBOD) [11].

Although there are other causes of serious childbirth-related infections in women during the postpartum period (for example, mastitis), this study focused on postpartum sepsis caused by endometritis due to its dominant role in severe cases of illness or death[6].

The purpose of the study: to evaluate changes in blood tests of women with postpartum sepsis.

Materials and methods. 96 women with physiological and pathological course of pregnancy and childbirth were studied. They were divided into 3 representative groups.:

Group 1-patients with a physiological course of pregnancy and childbirth n=30.

Group 2- patients at risk of developing postpartum sepsis who underwent a comprehensive study with the inclusion of the biomarker presentin n=35

Group 3- patients at risk of developing postpartum sepsis who have not been predicted to develop sepsis by studying biomarkers and timely treatment, n=31.

All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including:

- general and biochemical blood tests;
- extended coagulogram: APTT, prothrombin time (PV), international normalized ratio (INR), fibrinogen, platelet levels, D-dimer, antithrombin III.

Statistical processing was performed using the SPSS v.25 software. The differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results. A hemostasiogram, or coagulogram, includes a set of parameters characterizing the state of the blood coagulation system. In sepsis, activation of the coagulation cascade is accompanied by the development of disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC syndrome), which is manifested by characteristic changes in laboratory tests. The study of these changes makes it possible to improve the accuracy of early diagnosis of sepsis and timely initiation of therapy.

The main parameters of the hemostasiogram were studied in all the examined women, and the results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Comparative hemostasis parameters in pregnant women at risk of developing postpartum sepsis

Indicators		Research groups		
		1-группа, n=30	2-группа, n=35	3-группа, n=31
Hemoglobin, g/l 120-140 g/l		90,87±1,98	95,97±1,71*↑	89,48±2,12↔^
Red blood cells, 10 ¹² /l		2,87±0,10	3,19±0,06*↑	2,90±0,07↔^
Color indicator, units		0,85±0,01	0,85±0,01↔	0,85±0,01↔
White blood cells, 10 ⁹ /l		8,54±0,22	11,4±0,51*↑	11,6±0,78*↑
Lymphocytes, %		27,5±0,45	26,8±0,28*↓	26,87±0,59*↓
Monocytes, %		3,33±0,12	3,0±0,17*↓	2,87±0,14*↓
Eosinophils, %		1,0±0,01	1,51±0,16*↑	1,52±0,14*↑
Basophils, %		0,02±0,00	0,20±0,1*↑	0,25±0,03*↑
Neutrophils	segment-core	49,87±1,38	67,06±0,47*↑	67,94±0,42*↑
	rod-shaped	1,60±0,13	2,20±0,10*↑	2,26±0,13*↑
Platelets		194,2±3,02	331,5±22,27*↑	375,06±29,13*↑
LII, ed		0,88±0,01	0,88±0,08↔	1,15±0,06*↑^
ESR, mm/hour		4,39±0,48	21,2±1,50*↑	26,3±2,75*↑^
Hematocrit		30,37±0,54	31,57±0,55*↑	31,61±0,66*↑

Note: * sign-significant difference in relation to the control data, ↑↓-direction of changes, ^-sign of significant difference between groups 2 and 3, ↔-no significant difference.

In patients with postpartum sepsis at an early stage of the disease, the following characteristic changes in hemostasis parameters were observed compared with the control group (Table 2)

Table 2

Comparative coagulogram parameters in pregnant women at risk of developing postpartum sepsis

Indicator	The main group (n = 66)	Control group (n = 30)	p-value
Activated partial thromboplastin time, sec	43,1 ± 4,6	32,8 ± 3,9	<0,01
PT, sec	17,2 ± 2,1	13,9 ± 1,7	<0,01
International Normalized Relations	1,38 ± 0,12	1,04 ± 0,09	<0,01
Platelets, ×10 ⁹ /l	118,6 ± 27,3	221,4 ± 35,6	<0,01
Fibrinogen, g/l	3,6 ± 1,1	4,2 ± 0,9	0,07
D-dimer, mcg/ml	2,71 ± 1,3	0,46 ± 0,2	<0,01
Antithrombin III, %	64,8 ± 8,4	91,2 ± 7,9	<0,01

Prothrombin is a key protein in the coagulation cascade involved in the conversion of fibrinogen to fibrin through the activation of thrombin. Given that an increase in prothrombin levels is associated with an increased risk of thrombosis, its quantification in the coagulogram is of significant diagnostic importance. According to the results of our study, patients in the second group had a statistically significant increase in prothrombin levels by 1.06 times compared with the first group: $18.17 \pm 0.22\%$ versus $12.40 \pm 0.27\%$, respectively ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, an analysis of the comparative results of the coagulogram study in pregnant women at risk of developing postpartum sepsis showed that in pregnant women of the 2nd group, where early diagnosis with presepsin and timely treatment were performed, such coagulogram parameters as PT, PTI, fibrinogen remained significantly high, respectively by 1.06, 1.08 and 1.04 times relative to the normal data. values ($P0.05$).

The most significant markers of early sepsis were an increase in D-dimer levels, an increase in APTT, and a decrease in platelet levels. Moderate thrombocytopenia and decreased antithrombin III activity were observed in all patients with sepsis, indicating depletion of the anticoagulant potential of the blood.

The results obtained confirm the presence of pronounced coagulopathy already at the onset of postpartum sepsis. At the initial stage, a hypercoagulable state prevails, reflecting a systemic inflammatory reaction. An elongation of APTT and PV, an increase in D-dimer indicate activation of the coagulation and fibrinolytic systems, while a decrease in antithrombin III and platelet levels indicates depletion of reserves and the possible development of DIC syndrome.

A decrease in fibrinogen levels was not observed in all cases, which indicates its low sensitivity at an early stage of sepsis. On the contrary, the level of D-dimer turned out to be the most sensitive indicator, demonstrating a significant excess of the control values even in the absence of a pronounced clinical picture.

Timely assessment of coagulopathy allows doctors to decide on the initiation of intensive care and monitoring in the intensive care unit. Thus, an extended hemostasis chart should be included in the algorithm for early diagnosis of postpartum sepsis.

Conclusion. A hemostasiogram is an important tool for early diagnosis of postpartum sepsis. Changes in the hemostasis system — prolongation of APTT and PV, decrease in platelets and antithrombin III, increase in D-dimer — can serve as early markers of septic condition before the development of severe clinical symptoms. Regular monitoring of these indicators allows timely detection of the onset of the systemic inflammatory process and initiation of necessary therapy, which significantly improves the prognosis for the patient. Changes in the parameters of the blood coagulation system can precede clinical manifestations, allowing timely initiation of treatment and reducing the risk of an adverse outcome. An integrated approach, including laboratory and clinical assessment, is the key to successful diagnosis and treatment of septic conditions in the postpartum period.

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